

Variations in Night Sky Brightness in Urban Areas of Japan and Their Factors

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Abstract: Light pollution is one of the increasingly serious global issues. While simulation studies on a global scale have been conducted, research on regional-scale changes in night sky brightness around Japan remains insufficient. This study developed a model capable of estimating night sky brightness closer to actual observations than previous research by performing radiative transfer calculations and comparing them with domestic citizen observation data collected by Japan's Ministry of the Environment. The results also revealed that the contribution of environmental factors causing light pollution varies between cities. This demonstrates that an approach considering region-specific environmental factors is essential for accurately understanding the reality of light pollution and implementing effective countermeasures.

Keywords: radiation transfer model; aerosol; distribution of night sky brightness.

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